

STUDY ON PREVALENCE OF POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME IN YOUNG UNMARRIED GIRLS PRESENTING IN GYNECOLOGY OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT WITH SYMPTOMS

Sehrish Qalander^{*1}, Abida Ashraf², Shafaq Mannan³

^{*1,3}Cmh Gujranwala Obstetrics & gynaecology Pakistan

²Assistant professor Obstetrics & gynaecology CMH Gujranwala

^{*1}sehrishshaykh786@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Sehrish Qalander

Abstract

Background: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a leading endocrine disorder among young women, often presenting with menstrual irregularities, acne, hirsutism, and metabolic concerns. Despite its high prevalence, evidence on unmarried adolescents in Pakistan remains limited.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of PCOS and its associated clinical, lifestyle, and biochemical factors in unmarried girls presenting with gynecological symptoms.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, CMH Gujranwala from 03-02-2025 till 03-07-2025 following ethical approval. Using non-probability consecutive sampling, 200 unmarried girls aged 15–30 years with symptoms such as irregular cycles, hirsutism, acne, or weight gain were enrolled. Demographic and clinical data were collected, hirsutism scores were assessed, and blood samples were analyzed for luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH). Ultrasound was performed to detect ovarian morphology. PCOS was diagnosed according to Rotterdam criteria and operational definitions. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25; $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results: PCOS was diagnosed in 45% ($n = 90$) of participants. Sedentary lifestyle (74.4% vs. 52.7%, $p < 0.001$), frequent consumption of fast/street food ($p = 0.001$), family history of PCOS (44.4% vs. 25.5%, $p = 0.005$), and ovarian cysts (44.4% vs. 17.3%, $p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with PCOS. Girls with PCOS also had higher hirsutism scores (10.40 ± 3.76 vs. 5.60 ± 2.05 , $p < 0.001$), elevated LH (8.70 ± 3.82 vs. 2.56 ± 1.13 IU/L, $p < 0.001$), and raised LH/FSH ratios (2.32 ± 1.58 vs. 0.52 ± 0.32 , $p < 0.001$). Age, age at menarche, BMI, and FSH levels did not differ significantly.

Conclusion: In this study 45% of unmarried symptomatic girls were diagnosed with PCOS. Sedentary habits, poor diet, family history, and ovarian cysts were key risk factors, while hirsutism and hormonal imbalances distinguished affected individuals. These findings underscore the importance of early screening, lifestyle modification, and context-appropriate diagnostic criteria in adolescent girls.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine disorder among women of reproductive age and a chief cause of subfertility attributed to ovulation. Besides, lack of knowledge about PCOS, its treatment, and lifestyle changes influence the prognosis.⁽¹⁾ In Pakistan, recent studies estimate the prevalence of PCOS in adolescent and young unmarried girls at approximately 37.3%-55.6%, with up to one in five presenting with symptoms such as menstrual irregularities, acne, and hirsutism in gynecology outpatient departments.^(2, 3) Polycystic Ovary Syndrome is estimated by the World Health Organization to impact 8-13% of women in their reproductive years, with over 50% of these cases remaining undiagnosed.⁽⁴⁾

According to the Rotterdam consensus, PCOS is defined by the presence of two of three of the following criteria: oligo-anovulation, hyperandrogenism and polycystic ovaries (≥ 12 follicles measuring 2-9 mm in diameter and/or an ovarian volume > 10 mL in at least one ovary). The sonographic criteria were based on a study published in 2003 by Jonard et al., where patients with PCOS were found to have significantly more follicles in the 2-5 mm range than a control group comprised of women with tubal or male factor infertility.^(5,6)

The prevalence of PCOS, one of the most common female endocrine disorders, depends on the diagnostic criteria used and the study population (referral or unselected). It is also thought to be influenced by race and ethnicity.⁽⁷⁾ The major changes in physical appearance, obesity, along with menstrual irregularity have been found to be the main contributing factor of psychological dilemma. PCOS negative impact is always underestimated and dominates on women's life and may lead to a risk for serious anxiety and psychological disorder.⁽⁸⁾

Rationale of this study is to determine the frequency of PCOS in unmarried girls presenting in with symptoms. PCOS can lead to infertility in later life in such cases and increase burden on obstetricians and gynecologists. Literature showed that the risk of PCOS varies in unmarried girls belong to different regions of the world. But, the evidence is limited and no study has been done before in local population. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a study in local population to get data against extent of problem in

girls living in local community. This will help us to improve our knowledge and practice and we will be able to implement diagnostic and preventive methods to promptly diagnose and manage in unmarried girls with symptoms to lessen down the adverse outcomes of PCOS in their current and later.

Method

After obtaining ethical clearance from the institutional ethical review board this cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, CMH Gujranwala, from 03-02-2025 till 03-07-2025. A sample size of 200 unmarried girls was calculated using the WHO calculator with a 95% confidence level, 5.5% absolute precision, and an expected prevalence of PCOS of 18.33%. Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed for sample selection. Females aged 15-30 years who presented with symptoms such as abnormal menstrual cycles, hirsutism (hirsutism score > 8), acne, or weight gain were included. Girls with insufficient blood samples, incomplete surveys, prior hair removal procedures, thyroid dysfunction (TSH > 5 IU/L), or a history of recurrent PCOS or treatment were excluded. After obtaining informed consent, demographic details (age, BMI, age at menarche, duration of symptoms, lifestyle, diet pattern, occupation, and family history of PCOS) were recorded. Each participant underwent clinical assessment, including hirsutism scoring, and provided blood samples for LH and FSH measurement. Ultrasound examinations were performed to assess ovarian morphology, including the presence of cysts. PCOS was diagnosed according to the Rotterdam criteria and operational definition (LH/FSH ratio > 1 , ≥ 20 follicles of 2-8 mm, or ovarian volume ≥ 10 cm³). All information was documented on a structured proforma.

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Normality of quantitative variables was assessed using the Shapiro Wilk test. Quantitative variables such as age, age at menarche, BMI, duration of symptoms, and hirsutism score were presented as mean \pm standard deviation for normally distributed

data and as median with interquartile range for non-normally distributed data. Qualitative variables including lifestyle, diet pattern, occupation, family history of PCOS, and PCOS status were presented as frequencies and percentages. For normally distributed variables, group comparisons were made using the independent samples *t*-test, while the Mann-Whitney *U* test was applied for non-normally distributed data. Data were stratified for age, age at menarche, BMI, lifestyle, diet pattern, occupation, duration of symptoms, family history of PCOS, and hirsutism score. Post-stratification, chi-square tests were used to compare categorical variables, and *p* ≤ .05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of the study participants. Mean age of girls was 21.83±230 years, mean age at menarche was 11.84±147 years. Mean body mass index of girls was 26.05±4.59 and mean duration of symptoms was 11.67±6.50 weeks. Most girls reported sedentary lifestyles (62.5%), with fast food (38.5%) and homemade diets (33.5%) as common patterns. A majority followed diet plans (83.5%). Students comprised the largest occupational group (69.5%). Family history of PCOS was reported

in 34%, and ovarian cysts were present in 29.5%. The mean hirsutism score was 12.64, and mean LH, FSH, and LH/FSH ratio were 5.32 IU/L, 4.92 IU/L, and 1.32 respectively (Table-1). Figure 1 demonstrates that nearly half of the unmarried girls in the sample were diagnosed with PCOS. (Figure-1) Girls with PCOS (n = 90) had a slightly higher mean age (21.96 vs. 21.74 years) and earlier menarche, though differences were non-significant. BMI did not differ significantly between groups. Lifestyle was significantly associated with PCOS, with 74.4% of PCOS girls reporting sedentary habits versus 52.7% in non-PCOS. Diet patterns showed PCOS girls consumed more street and fast food, while non-PCOS favored homemade food. Occupation differed, with more students in the PCOS group, and family history of PCOS was more common (44.4% vs. 25.5%). Ovarian cysts were significantly higher in PCOS (44.4% vs. 17.3%). Hirsutism scores were markedly elevated in PCOS (10.40±3.76) compared to non-PCOS (5.60±2.05), *p*-value<0.001. Hormonal profiles showed significantly higher LH and LH/FSH ratios in PCOS, while FSH did not differ. (Table-2)

Table-I: Patients Charactersitics (n=200)

	Frequency	Percent
Life Style	Active	33 16.5%
	Sedentary	125 62.5%
	Sports/Exercise	42 21%
Diet Pattern	Home made	67 33.5%
	Fast Food	77 38.5%
	Street Food	56 28%
Diet Plan	Diet Plan	167 83.5%
	Skip meals	33 16.5%
Occupation	Student	139 69.5%
	Job	29 14.5%
	Nothing	32 16%
F/H PCOS	Yes	68 34%
	No	132 66%
Ovarian Cysts	Yes	59 29.5%
	No	141 70.5%
Hirsutism score	Mean±SD	7.76±3.79
	Median(IQR)	6.9(5.07)
LH (IU/L)	Mean±SD	5.32±4.07

	Median(IQR)	3.40(5.69)
FSH (IU/L)	Mean±SD	4.92±1.96
	Median(IQR)	4.8(2.58)
LH/FSH Ratio	Mean±SD	1.32±1.40
	Median(IQR)	0.49(1.15)

Figure-I: Polycystic Ovarian syndrome among young unmarried girls (n=200)

Table-II: Comparison of characteristics in relation to Polycystic ovarian syndrome among study participants

		Poly Cystic Ovarian Syndrome		p-value
		Yes	No	
		90	110	
Age		21.96±2.34	21.74±2.29	0.499 ^(m)
Age at menarche		11.78±1.44	11.90±1.50	0.565 ^(m)
Body Mass Index		25.82±4.82	26.25±4.42	0.508 ^(t)
Life Style	Active	16(17.8%)	17(15.5%)	<0.001 ^{*(c)}
	Sedentary	67(74.4%)	58(52.7%)	
	Sports/Exercise	7(7.8%)	35(31.8%)	
Diet Pattern	Home made	19(21.1%)	48(43.6%)	0.001 ^{*(c)}
	Fast Food	37(41.1%)	40(36.4%)	
	Street Food	34(37.8%)	22(20%)	
Diet Plan	Yes	76(84.4%)	91(82.7%)	0.849 ^(c)
	Skip meals	14(15.6%)	19(17.3%)	
Occupation	Student	67(74.4%)	72(65.5%)	0.043 ^{*(c)}
	Job	15(16.7%)	14(12.7%)	
	Nothing	8(8.9%)	24(21.8%)	
F/H PCOS		40(44.4%)	28(25.5%)	0.005 ^{*(c)}
Ovarian Cysts		40(44.4%)	19(17.3%)	<0.001 ^{*(c)}
Hirsutism score	Mean±SD	10.40±3.76	5.60±2.05	<0.001 ^{*(m)}
	Median(IQR)	10.30(5.25)	5.6(2.33)	
LH (IU/L)	Mean±SD	8.70±3.82	2.56±1.13	<0.001 ^{*(m)}
	Median(IQR)	8.50(5.03)	2.57(1.15)	
FSH (IU/L)	Mean±SD	4.75±2.13	5.07±1.81	0.245 ^(t)
	Median(IQR)	4.45(3)	5.2(2.25)	

LH/FSH Ratio	Mean±SD	2.32±1.58	0.52±0.32	<0.001 ^{*(m)}
	Median(IQR)	1.75(1.87)	0.49(0)	

Note: (t): Independent sample t-test (m): Mann Whitney U test (c): Chi Square test (*): p-value <0.05 (Statistically significant)

Discussion

The present study provides a detailed profile of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) among young, unmarried women, highlighting lifestyle, dietary, familial, and biochemical factors associated with the syndrome. Results of this study showed that 45% prevalence of PCOS among unmarried girls. Recent Pakistani studies show that the prevalence of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) varies widely depending on region, population, and diagnostic criteria, but is generally high among young women. Local studies from Pakistan reported the prevalence as low as 10.9%⁽⁹⁾ to as high as 48.5% and 55.9%.^(3, 10, 11) In contrast, a community adolescent survey in urban and rural Pakistan found 26.7% prevalence using the Rotterdam criteria in girls 13–19 years old.⁽³⁾ Prevalence rates in Indian studies vary widely, from 3.7% (Lucknow, North India) to 22.5% (Mumbai, Western India) among adolescents and young women, depending on diagnostic criteria and population sampled. The pooled prevalence in Indian women is generally 10–20% using Rotterdam criteria, and lower (5–8%) with NIH criteria.^(12, 13) A study of unmarried females aged 16–24 attending outpatient clinics found a 55.6% prevalence of PCOS, which is even higher than result of this study.⁽¹⁴⁾ The variation in PCOS prevalence may be attributed to differences in sample selection, diagnostic criteria, lifestyle factors, and the degree of urbanization. In the present study, it is possible that more symptomatic and high-risk individuals were included, which could have inflated the prevalence compared to community-based samples. Moreover, the use of different diagnostic criteria, such as the Rotterdam criteria, can also influence reported prevalence rates.

Age, age at menarche, and BMI did not differ significantly between the PCOS and non-PCOS groups, reinforcing that PCOS may manifest across the weight spectrum in young women. This matches findings from a Pakistani study of medical students in which many PCOS cases had normal BMI.⁽²⁾

Variability across studies often reflects sampling window (early vs late adolescence) rather than a true etiologic shift. In this study the overall mean BMI was in the overweight range, reflecting the known association between PCOS and increased adiposity, which can worsen metabolic and reproductive outcomes.⁽¹⁵⁾ Kudesia et al. reported that younger South Asian women with a normal BMI presenting to infertility clinics had nearly six times higher odds of developing PCOS compared to their Caucasian counterparts.⁽¹⁶⁾

In this study a sedentary lifestyle was predominant among participants with PCOS, with 74.4% of affected individuals reporting low physical activity compared to 52.7% in non-PCOS counterparts (p<0.001). This aligns with broader research indicating that sedentary behavior and weight gain are significant contributors to PCOS development and severity, emphasizing the importance of early lifestyle interventions to mitigate risk and progression.^(3, 15, 17) Fast food and street food consumption were more common among PCOS cases, while a home-made diet was less frequent (21.1% vs. 43.6%, p=0.001), supporting evidence that unhealthy dietary patterns exacerbate metabolic and reproductive symptoms in PCOS.^(3, 18, 19) In this study a positive family history of PCOS was significantly higher in the affected group (44.4% vs. 25.5%, p-value=0.005), consistent with the established heritable component of the syndrome.⁽¹⁹⁾ Studies have reported significant association of family history and occurrence of PCOS.⁽²⁰⁾ In this study ovarian cysts and hirsutism were also more prevalent and severe among PCOS cases, with higher mean hirsutism scores (10.40±3.76 vs. 5.60±2.05, p-value<0.001), reflecting the central role of hyperandrogenism in PCOS pathophysiology.⁽²¹⁾ As far as biochemical markers are concerned in this study Significantly elevated luteinizing hormone (LH) levels and LH/FSH ratios were observed in the PCOS group (LH: 8.70±3.82 vs. 2.56±1.13 IU/L; LH/FSH ratio: 2.32±1.58 vs. 0.52±0.32; both p-

value<0.001), consistent with the classical endocrine profile of PCOS.⁽²²⁾ These hormonal imbalances are linked to ovulatory dysfunction and hyperandrogenism, key features of the syndrome.⁽²²⁾
²³⁾ Kumayl Abbas Meghji in his study reported significantly higher level of FSH and LH level among PCOS cases.⁽²⁾ Similar trend was reported by Humaira Jadoon.⁽³⁾ Current international guidance warns that **LH/FSH ratio should not be used alone for diagnosis** in adolescents because of pubertal variability, but an elevated ratio can **support** the clinical picture alongside hyperandrogenism and cycle disturbance.^(24, 25) This study has few limitations like small sample size, symptomatic patients which may inflate the prevalence when compared with general population. Given the cross-sectional nature of this study, it is not possible to establish a causal relationship between diet and lifestyle and the development of Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome; rather, only an association can be inferred. The application of ultrasound and the luteinizing hormone to follicle-stimulating hormone ratio in diagnosing adolescents is contentious and may contribute to over diagnosis. The results of this study cannot be generalized for the whole population. Treatment options given to these adolescent patients were not studied.

Conclusion

Results of this study showed that 45% of unmarried adolescent girls with gynecological symptoms in outpatient clinics were diagnosed with PCOS. Significant factors associated with PCOS were sedentary behavior and frequent consumption of fast or street food. A family history of PCOS and the presence of ovarian cysts were also identified as significant risk factors. Elevated hirsutism scores, along with increased luteinizing hormone and LH/follicle-stimulating hormone ratios, effectively distinguished girls with PCOS from those without.

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